

Empowerment and Strengthening the Role of Women in Efforts to Reduce the Incidence of Early Marriage and Detection of its Health Impacts on the Community

Lestari Sudaryanti¹

Midwifery Study Programme Faculty of Medicine,
Airlangga University
Surabaya, Indonesia

Joni Haryanto²

Imam Susilo³

Midwifery Study Programme Faculty of Medicine,
Airlangga University
Surabaya, Indonesia

Abstract:- Gedang Kulud Village, Cerme Sub-district, Gresik Regency is an agricultural area with a fairly religious community culture and has serious problems with the high number of early marriages, as well as environmental sanitation problems, but has the potential to develop SME industries that can support the progress of the village. Gedang Kulud village cadres are extraordinary people who have high dedication and commitment to the progress of their village. This is an opportunity for solutions to problems in Gedang Kulud village, to be able to solve problems independently, in synergy with local capabilities and potential. Training health cadres to become development innovators provides an opportunity for Gedang Kulud village to progress and develop sustainably. Health cadres are cadres chosen by the community to be Posyandu organisers. Innovator cadres are health cadres who drive community participation in the health sector, especially in efforts to mature the age of marriage. Innovator cadres are trained and equipped with various skills so that they can become community participation leaders who are able to become role models for the community, disseminate knowledge, provide assistance, and monitor the progress of the community members they assist. In 2015, 83.3% of all marriages in Gedang Kulud village involved women under the age of 20 and 44.4% involved women under the age of 20. Some of the reasons for the high rate of early marriage are the low socioeconomic status of the community, the myth of the "virgin kasep" if married above the age of 20, and the fear of violating ethical and religious norms if a girl is not married off immediately. Women who marry at a young age have longer exposure to pregnancy risks. The lower the age at which a woman becomes pregnant, the greater the health risks; the risk of death from pregnancy is twice as high in adolescent girls aged 15-19 years compared to women aged 20-24 years. A woman who gives birth before the age of 15 years has a 5 times higher risk of dying during childbirth compared to women aged 20 years and older (Intan, 2012). Maternal deaths in pregnant and giving birth women under the age of 20 years are 2 - 5 times higher than maternal deaths that occur at the age of 20 - 29 years. (Romauli, 2009). Complications from

pregnancy and childbirth are the leading cause of death for women aged 15 to 19 years in developing countries. Increasing community empowerment and strengthening the role of women, in order to reduce the incidence of early marriage and its health impacts from the point of view of health, economy and religion, in Gedang Kulud village, Cerme sub-district, Gresik Regency, is the aim of the implementation of this community service.

Keywords:- Component; Formatting; Style; Styling; Insert.

I. INTRODUCTION

The superior potential of Gedangkulut Village is in the agriculture and trade sectors, where most of the population are farmers. The economy of Gedangkulut Village is supported by the agriculture, trade, services and home industry sectors. The majority of the population of Gedangkulut Village is Muslim, while most of the education is elementary school graduates.

Legally, child marriage is legitimised by Law No. 1/1974 on Marriage. This law allows children as young as 16 years old to marry, as stated in article 7 paragraph 1, "Marriage is only permitted if the male party has reached 19 (nineteen) years of age, and the female party has reached 16 (sixteen) years of age." Article 26 of Law No. 23/2002 on Child Protection requires parents to protect their children from early marriage, but this article, like the Marriage Law, has no provision for criminal sanctions, making it almost meaningless in protecting children from the threat of early marriage. Socio-economic problems in early marriage usually mean that couples who marry early do not have economic readiness. The older a person is, the more likely it is that maturity in the socio-economic field will also be more evident because generally with increasing age there will be a stronger urge to seek support. Economic problems in early marriage are the main reason for divorce. (Romauli, 2009). In 2015, 83.3% of all marriages in Gedang Kulud Village involved women aged less than 20 years and 44.4% involved women aged less than 20 years. Some of the reasons for the high number of early marriages are the low socioeconomic status of the community, the myth that people believe about

"virgin kasep" if married above the age of 20, and the fear of violating ethical and religious norms if a girl is not married immediately.

The ideal age for marriage is 20-25 years old for women and 25-30 years old for men, because at that age the woman's reproductive organs are ready and mature to become pregnant, which will prevent pregnancy with risks or complications. Women who marry at a young age have a longer time to the risk of pregnancy. The lower the age at which a woman becomes pregnant, the greater the health risks; the risk of death from pregnancy is twice as high for adolescent girls aged 15-19 years compared to women aged 20-24 years. A woman who gives birth before the age of 15 has a 5 times higher risk of dying during childbirth compared to women aged 20 years and older (Intan, 2012). Maternal deaths in pregnant and giving birth women under the age of 20 years are 2 - 5 times higher than maternal deaths that occur at the age of 20 - 29 years. (Romauli, 2009). Complications from pregnancy and childbirth are the leading cause of death for women aged 15 to 19 years in developing countries.

Women who have their first sex under the age of 20 have a greater risk of cervical cancer. Sadewa (2014) in his research in Semarang found that there was a relationship between the incidence of cervical cancer and age at marriage. Women who marry before the age of 20 have a higher risk of cervical cancer than those who marry above the age of 20. Khalaf, et al. (2015) in their research in Iraq found that age of marriage less than 18 years is a specific determinant of the presence of abnormal Papanicolaou test results.

➤ *Problem Formulation*

The incidence of early marriage in Gedang Kulud village is a complex problem and requires comprehensive and cross-sectoral handling. So that the formulation of problems in Gedang Kulud village can be identified as follows:

- Low community knowledge of the adverse effects of early marriage from health, economic and religious perspectives
- Low community awareness to prevent early marriage
- Low community capacity for early prevention of the adverse health effects of early marriage
- Low community knowledge to develop the woven sarong handicraft industry to be more economically valuable and market the results of their creativity.
- Low community awareness of clean and healthy living behaviour (PHBS) in their family environment, to prevent the impact of weaving industry activities on health.

II. EASE OF USE

A. *Cadre of Innovators*

Health cadres are cadres chosen by the community to organise the Posyandu. Innovator cadres are health cadres who drive community participation in the health sector, especially in efforts to mature the age of marriage. Innovator

cadres are trained and equipped with various skills so that they can become community participation leaders who are able to become role models for the community, disseminate knowledge, provide assistance, and monitor the progress of the community members they assist.

B. *Maturing Age of Marriage Factors Affecting Age at Marriage Education*

Parents' education level is closely related to the economic status of the family. Research conducted by (Chloe, Thapa, & Achmad, 2007) in Nepal states that higher levels of parental education are more successful in delaying marriage at an early age. More educated parents are more able to accept modern values and give their children the freedom to determine their own mate.

➤ *Socio-Economic*

Early marriage is closely related to poverty. Poverty is characterised by low income, lack of education, lack of health, and lack of assets (Oyortey & Pobi, 2003). Research conducted by Sariroh (2004) in Pasuruan Regency found that one of the factors leading to marriage at a young age is a low economy (poor).

➤ *Culture*

In Indonesia, for women, marriage is a matter of long-established values conditioned by culture, religion and the surrounding environment that make women obliged to enter the institution of marriage. In a patriarchal culture, marriage not only functions as a social identity and an increase in social status but also so that women appear to be perfect, namely becoming a wife and then a mother (Kartika, 2002). The pattern of marriage in Indonesian society is very diverse, according to the culture and norms prevailing in the community. Cultural factors are closely related to local customs. In Indonesia, each region has its own customs, among others: in Javanese society, they quickly marry off their daughters because they are ashamed that their children are considered old virgins.

➤ *Knowledge*

Knowledge or cognitive is a very important domain in shaping a person's actions (overt behaviour). Behaviour based on knowledge will be more lasting than behaviour that is not based on knowledge. Rogers' research in Notoatmojo (2007) concluded that behaviour change does not always pass through the above stages. *If the acceptance of new behaviour or the adoption of behaviour through such a process is based on knowledge, awareness and positive attitudes (long lasting). Conversely, if the behaviour is not based on knowledge and awareness, it will not last long.*

➤ *Family Perception (Parents)*

The family can be said to be a body of a social body that functions to direct a person's effective life in the family a person can experience disappointment, get affection and maybe even reproaches. A calm family atmosphere and full of outpouring of affection from the adults around him, will allow adolescents to develop naturally and achieve happiness. Meanwhile, a household atmosphere full of conflict will negatively affect the personality and happiness

of adolescents, which in the end they vent their soul feelings in various associations and deviant behaviour (Al-Mighwar, 2006).

➤ *Virginity Value*

The value of virginity to do anything, including intercourse. Dating as a process of personality development of a teenager due to attraction between the opposite sex. However, in the development of culture, it tends to be ignorant of teenage dating styles. As a result, teenagers tend to have premarital sex. Some factors that cause promiscuity among adolescents are; religious and faith factors, environmental factors such as parents, friends, neighbours and the media, factors of minimal knowledge plus excessive curiosity, and also factors of changing times (Sarwono, 2006; Magadi & Agwanda, 2009) Freedom of association between the sexes in adolescents can easily be witnessed in everyday life, especially in big cities. Marriage in adolescence eventually causes problems no less complicated. So in any situation, sexual behaviour in adolescents is never beneficial, even though adolescence is a period of transition to adulthood (Sarwono, 2006).

• *Things that must be done according to (Nurjanah, Estiwidani, & Purnamaningrum, 2013), in preventing early marriage are:*

- ✓ Marriage law
- ✓ Mentoring teenagers and explaining about sex education
- ✓ Provide counselling to parents and the community
- ✓ Co-operate with religious and community leaders
- ✓ Pilot village model for maturing the age of marriage

C. *VIA Examination*

The group of risk factors for cervical cancer are having first sexual intercourse at a young age (before the age of 18 years), patients or sexual partners have genital condyloma (warts), past partners of sexual partners have cervical cancer or abnormal cells, sexual partners have penile cancer and sexual partners who are not circumcised. Things to watch out for are if there is yellow vaginal discharge, odour, pain during sexual intercourse and abnormal vaginal bleeding (Juanda & Kesuma, 2015). Cervical cancer is the second most frequent cause of cancer in women in the world. But due to limitations of screening and therapy, many deaths arise especially in women in developing countries. An effective method for early detection of pre-cancerous lesions with cytology (Pap Smear), but limited manpower, money, and poor health systems cause early detection with pap smears to be limited in developing countries (WHO, 2013). The implementation of preventive and control programmes against cervical cancer contributes to the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals through sexual and reproductive health by improving women's health (WHO, 2013).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used by the proposer is the partnership method, namely the village midwife, village nurse and village officials as partners to jointly have responsibility for the Community Service programme with the title "Empowerment and strengthening the role of women in efforts to reduce the incidence of early marriage and detection of its health effects in the weaving artisan community in Gedang Kulud village, Cerme District, Gresik Regency", can be completed on time. Specifically, the methods used are socialisation, demonstration, on the job training, so that various elements of management can be completed properly.

The proposer understands the socio-culture and religion of the partners in this Community Service, so there is no need for serious problems, and if there are problems, they will immediately resolve them in a family manner, deliberation and consensus.

IV. DISCUSSION

In terms of marriage, the 2007 Indonesian Demographic and Health Survey (IDHS) reported that of 6,341 women aged 15-19 years, 12.8% were married and of 6,681 women aged 20-24 years, 59.2% were married. UNFPA considers 15-24 years old as youth and 15-19 years old as late adolescence, so it is clear that adolescents according to the 2007 IDHS are getting married at a younger age. According to the 2007 IDHS report, 4.3% of women at the age of 15 had married for the first time (BKKBN, 2007). According to the United Nations Development Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), Indonesia is the 37th country with a high percentage of young marriages and the second highest in ASEAN after Cambodia. In 2010, there were 158 countries where the minimum legal age of marriage for women was 18 years and above, but in Indonesia the minimum age for women was 16 years. Early marriage is risky due to insufficient readiness from health, mental-emotional, educational, socio-economic, and reproductive aspects (Ministry of Health, 2014). Indonesia's median age at first marriage is 19.8 years old, while the median age at first marriage in rural areas is 17.9 years old. This figure indicates that half of couples of childbearing age in Indonesia marry under the age of 20 (Ahmad, 2013). From the results of the study, maternal respondents obtained a marriage age of <1 year by 0%, maternal respondents with a marriage age of 1-8 years by 8%, maternal respondents with a marriage age of 3-10 years by 49% and maternal respondents with a marriage age of > 10 years by 43%.

➤ *Mother's Education Level*

Maternal education determines most of a person's knowledge, good education will have an impact on a person's knowledge. Knowledge or cognitive is a very important domain in shaping a person's actions (overt behaviour). Behaviour based on knowledge will be more lasting than behaviour that is not based on knowledge. From the results of the study, the mother's respondent obtained an education level of 0%, the mother's respondent with

elementary school education level was 21%, the mother's respondent with junior high school education level was 56% and the mother's respondent with high school education level was 23%.

Rogers' research in Notoatmojo (2007) concluded that behaviour change does not always go through the above stages. If the acceptance of new behaviour or the adoption of behaviour through such a process is based on knowledge, awareness and positive attitudes (long lasting). Conversely, if the behaviour is not based on knowledge and awareness, it will not last long. According to Notoatmojo (2007), knowledge is covered in the cognitive domain with 6 levels, namely:

- **Know.** Defined as remembering something material that has been previously learned. Included in this level of knowledge is a recall of a specific of all the material learned or stimuli that have been received.
- **Comprehension.** Understanding is defined as an ability to explain correctly about a known object and be able to interpret the material correctly.
- **Application.** Application is defined as the ability to use material that has been learnt in real situations or conditions.
- **Analysis.** Analysis is the ability to break down material or an object into components but still within an organisational structure.
- **Synthesis.** Synthesis shows an ability to put or connect parts in a new overall form. In other words, synthesis is an ability to formulate new formulations from existing formulations.
- **Evaluation.** This evaluation relates to the ability to make an assessment of a material or object of assessment based on an existing criteria.

Unhappiness in marriage is mostly due to the fact that most couples who enter into marriage have no mental preparation in the real sense. They are not equipped with enough, just advice and short sentences. They think that with love and sex they will be able to satisfy all the wants and needs of their wives. Women also think like that (Nurwati, 2003).

➤ *Income Level*

Early marriage is closely related to poverty. Poverty is characterised by low income, lack of education, lack of health, and lack of assets (Oyortey & Pobi, 2003).

From the results of the research, the mother's respondents obtained an income level of > 2 million by 8%, mother's respondents with an income level of 1-2 million by 65%, and mother's respondents with an income level of < 1 million by 27%. Research conducted by Chariroh (2004) in Pasuruan Regency found that one of the factors causing marriage at a young age is a low economy (poor).

➤ *Iva Screening Results*

Cervical cancer is the second most common cause of cancer in women worldwide. But due to limitations in screening and therapy, many deaths occur especially in

women in developing countries. An effective method for early detection of pre-cancerous lesions is cytology (Pap smear), but limited manpower, money, and poor health systems mean that early detection by pap smear is limited in developing countries (WHO, 2013). Newer technologies offer a comprehensive way to treat cervical cancer by increasing the availability and screening of an alternative called IVA (Inspection Visual Acetate) and a vaccine against HPV (Human papillomavirus) to prevent cervical cancer from progressing further. The implementation of preventive and control programmes against cervical cancer contributes to the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals through sexual and reproductive health by improving women's health (WHO, 2013).

Visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA) is an examination in which the examiner (doctor / midwife / paramedic) observes the cervix that has been given 3-5% acetic acid / vinegar acid inspecifically and seen with the naked eye. Visual Inspection with Acetic Acid (VIA) is an early detection method for cervical cancer that is suitable for developing countries including Indonesia. Precancerous lesions will display a white spot colour called acetowhite epithelium (Juanda & Kesuma, 2015). The group of risk factors for cervical cancer are having first sexual intercourse at a young age (before the age of 18 years), patients or sexual partners have genital condyloma (warts), past partners of sexual partners have cervical cancer or abnormal cells, sexual partners have penile cancer and sexual partners who are not circumcised. (Juanda & Kesuma, 2015). From the results of the study, maternal respondents obtained positive VIA examination results by 41%, and maternal respondents with negative VIA examination results by 59%.

V. CONCLUSION

Efforts to prevent underage marriage are felt to be more optimal if community members participate in playing an active role in preventing underage marriage around them. The strategy between the government and the community is the most effective strategy at the moment to prevent underage marriage so that in the future it is hoped that there will be no more children who become victims of this marriage and Indonesian children can be more optimistic about their future (Alfyah, 2009).

➤ *Managerial Implications*

Things that must be done according to (Nurjanah, Estiwidani, & Purnamaningrum, 2013), in preventing early marriage are:

- *Marriage law*
- *Mentoring teenagers and explaining about sex education*
- *Provide counselling to parents and the community*
- *Co-operate with religious and community leaders*
- *Pilot village model for maturing the age of marriage.*

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ahmad, H. (2013). *Prevention of Early Marriage*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [2]. Alfiah. (2009). *The Causes of Early Marriage*. Jakarta: EGC. Retrieved 3 December, 2016
- [3]. Allan, J. P. (2007). *Faithful in Marriage*. Jakarta: Gunung Mulia.
- [4]. Al-Mighwar, M. (2006). *Adolescent Psychology*. Bandung: Pustaka Setia.
- [5]. Andrijono, S. K., & Aziz, F. (2006). In *Manual Book Management Training of Pre-Cervical Cancer Lesion* (pp. 20-26). Leiden: Leiden University Medical Centre. Retrieved 2 December, 2016
- [6]. BKKBN. (2005). *Women's reproductive rights are neglected Health Law needs to be improved*. Jakarta: National Family Planning Coordinating Board. Retrieved 2 December, 2016
- [7]. BKKBN. (2007). *Avoid Pregnancy 4 Too*. Jakarta: National Family Planning Coordinating Board. Retrieved 3 December, 2016
- [8]. Broutet, N., Dangou, J.-M., Fadhil, I., Lazdane, G., Luciani, S., Mathur, A., & Okero, A. (2013). *WHO guidelines for screening and treatment of precancerous lesions for cervical cancer prevention*. Switzerland: World Health Organisation. Retrieved December 1, 2016, from www.who.int/reproductivehealth/publications/cancers/screening_and_treatment_of_precancerous_
- [9]. Carr, K. C. (2004). *Cervical Cancer Screening in Low Resource Settings: Using Visual Inspection With Acetic Acid*. *J Midwifery Womens Health*, 49(4), 329-337. doi:10.1016/j.jmwh.2004.02.015
- [10]. Chariroh. (2004). *Factors Influencing the Marriage and Divorce Rate of Young Wives in Pasuruan*. Malang: University of Muhammadiyah Malang.
- [11]. Chloe, M., Thapa, S., & Achmad, S. (2007). *Early Marriage and Childbearing in Indonesia and Nepal*. USAID Organisation. Retrieved December 3, 2016, from <http://www.eastwestcenter.org/fileadmin/stored/pdfs/POPwp10815.pdf>
- [12]. Dariyo, A. (2004). *Psychology of Adolescent Development*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia.
- [13]. Department of Health. (2014). *Adolescent Reproductive Health Situation*. Jakarta: Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia.
- [14]. Retrieved 3 December, 2016
- [15]. Department of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. (2013). *Basic Health Research Report (Riskesdas)*. Jakarta: Ministry of Health. Retrieved 3 December, 2016
- [16]. Gokce, B., Ozsahin, A., & Zencir, M. (2006). *Determinants of Adolescent Pregnancy in an Urban Area in Turkey: A Population-Based Case-Control Study*. *Journal of Biosocial Science*, 301-311.
- [17]. Indonesia, P. R. (1974, January 2). *Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage*. Jakarta, Indonesia. Retrieved 3 December, 2016
- [18]. Indonesia, P. R. (2014). *Law No.35 of 2014 on the Amendment to Law No. 23 of 2002 on Child Protection*. Jakarta. Retrieved 3 December, 2016
- [19]. Intan, K. & Iwan, A. (2012). *Reproductive Health*. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.
- [20]. Juanda, D., & Kesuma, H. (2015). *IVA (Visual Inspection of Acetic Acid) Method for Cervical Cancer Prevention*. *JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND HEALTH*, 2, 169-174. Retrieved 1 December, 2016
- [21]. Kartika, S. (2002). *Profile of Women's Marriage in Indonesia*. Khalaf, M.K., et. al. (2015). *Association between Early Marriage and Other Sociomedical Characteristic with the Cervical Pap Smear Results in Iraqi Women*. *Journal Advances in Sexual Medicine* 5, 73-82
- [22]. National Cancer Committee (NCC). (2015). *Cervical Cancer Clinical Care Guidelines*. Jakarta: Indonesian Ministry of Health. Retrieved December 2, 2016, from <file:///C:/Users/Stephani%20Aurelia%20S/Downloads/312908704-PPKServiks-pdf.pdf>
- [23]. Kumalasari, I., et al. (2012). *Reproductive Health*. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.